

Wonder Lake, a Case Study¹

Wonder lake, is a typical Midwestern lake, formed by groundwater filling in a kettle depression left behind by a block of stagnant Wadena Lobe Ice. Drift thickness is around 100 feet in the area, and ranges from outwash to till clay (see **glacial map**). Below the drift, are two pre-Cambrian aged bedrock units, which have been previously tested positive in Iron Formation and a Gabbroic intrusion (see **geologic map**). Rocks have been tested positive towards 15 percent or more iron rock deposits, which is considered a moderate endowment of natural resource use. The Gabbroic intrusion contains the famous “black granite” highly demanded by households and construction projects (see **photo 1**). The lake itself is 35 feet deep, and hosts the typical Midwestern pink flora plants (see **photo 2**), as well as fauna species such as toads and colored ducks. Lake visitors have enjoyed the wildlife scenery which includes natural environmental habitats. However, Wonder lake’s special reputation has been the *Red Ailurus fulgens Class II Panda Bear*, most commonly referred to as *The Red Panda*, which are considered an unofficial semi-rare animal species (see **photo 4**).

Ms. Hillary E. Meribrown owns a 500 acre parcel of land², which is endowed with large wooded trees, suitable for multiple land uses, that was gifted to her by her grandfather’s estate (see **land ownership map**). The parcel has almost 1000 feet of shoreline on Wonder Lake’s north shore, and is quite valuable. Ms. Meribrown is 85 years old and in poor health, and recently her lawyer suggested that she might want to sell the parcel to pay for her medical expenses. The land parcel is partially divided between the iron formation and Gabbroic intrusion of natural resources. The neighborhood of Ms. Meribrown’s land parcel area includes several amenities: i) the national highway “*Highway 30*” is right behind the parcel, which is considered not very noisy highway except during national holidays, and has a rest area 1.5 miles way (see **photo 3**), ii) a dairy farm which is close-by, owned by a warm yet practical gentleman who has been a good friend of the late husband of Ms. Meribrown, and who has a quiet and relaxed neighborhood reputation, and who is successful and interested in expanding his dairy business (see **photo 6**), iii) a resort opposite the lake called “*Good Times Resort*” (see **photo 5**) which has been moderately successful and has a reputation of being family friendly and eco-friendly, and iv) several “big family” homeowners who have large extended families, and who have been occasionally using the nearby resort and buying their dairy products from the nearby dairy farm, and who are considered historical owners of the neighborhood.

¹ “Wonder Lake – A Case Study” is under Creative Learning Commons license for worldwide learning distribution. The case study was published at SERC - Science Education Resource Center, Project Kaleidoscope, TLE (Teaching and Learning Economics), with funding by U.S. National Science Foundation (NSF). Worldwide distribution provided by SERC of Carleton College, Minnesota, USA. This version of the case study has been adapted for in-class use and feasibility scenarios. Case written by Matthew F. Whitehill (Lake Superior College, Minnesota) and Tarek H. Selim (American University in Cairo).

² One “acre” is 4,047 m². The land parcel area is therefore 2 km². It is roughly 1 km by 2 km.

The nearby township has a small community that consists of around three thousand people, basic infrastructure, and services include a grocery store, gas station, pharmacy store, tools hardware store, bookstore for children, a small clinic, and a flower shop. A Town Hall Admin Building is located across from Wonder Lake.

Case Scenarios:

#1. REAL ESTATE COMPOUND: You would like to buy the land, and then subdivide it into 50 to 75 units or lots, and sell the lots with constructed real estate for housing, commercial, and other uses. You are targeting to design your project based on environmentally-friendly landscape architecture design. You wish to establish a real estate compound with good infrastructure. A friendly, peaceful and green compound community is your target. It is costly business to do so. However, you know that if you strike a good business deal from buying this parcel from the old lady, then you will have a massive real estate development potential, which will stand you to make a lot of money in a short period of time. You are not very much interested in wildlife conservation or natural habitats, except if they will somehow generate extra revenues. You actually don't live on the Wonder Lake neighborhood, but rather 50 miles away. You knew about this business potential when you were driving back home on *Highway 30* and saw the "Land Parcel for Sale" advertisement. You did actually visit Wonder Lake several years back, and you have had nice memories of it back then. Now, you find it attractive yet a bit risky due its complexity and being a large scale project. To combat massive costs, you will target the middle class customer segment. You are ambitious and highly motivated for this business deal. It could be your lifetime money breaker. At the outskirts of the real estate compound, you are planning of establishing a Big Mall next to the highway, with some cafes and restaurants open 24/7.

#2. DAIRY FARM– As the owner of the nearby dairy farm, you would like to buy the land to increase the size of your dairy farm in terms of area and annual yield. Your current dairy farm is ½ a mile away from Ms. Meribrown's parcel, and you have known her late husband quite well. You want to help Ms. Meribrown in her medical expenses, yet you are practical in nature and would help others socially. Your successful dairy farm has 100 milking cows. If you buy the land parcel from Ms. Meribrown, you would likely use the new land to grow hay to feed your cows in the winter months, and use a significant part of it for pasture meadow land for raising and breeding sheep and goats, which will open a new line of business. You prefer the community to stay undisturbed and relatively quiet. Recently, you started to have a strong opinion against urbanization and housing developments, because they yield less farmland for future generations, and create those fancy sky-houses which to you are just rigid and unnatural. You have devoted your entire life to dairy farm activities, so you have plenty of experience to expand your farm business. You plan to establish an attractive "dairy farm outlet" to sell dairy products in the neighborhood and besides the Highway.

#3. GLOBAL MINING COMPANY: You would like to buy the land outright, and then get the legal right to extract magnesium, copper, and other minerals. You are specialized in mining and not manufacturing, however you find the location attractive due to its immediate return on your business. You are a global company with branches in 75 countries across the globe, and therefore have a cost advantage due to economies of scale and access to finance. There are very few MNEs in such local communities, and there is social resistance to global companies in such communities as well, especially from the local family residents. You will use corporate social responsibility (CSR) projects in order to absorb the resistance from the community. You would likely import most jobs from abroad, using worldwide cross-border operations from other branches. Yet, you are considering to have upper level local managerial positions. Your global company has a good financial position. Your main goal is shareholder dividends. You strongly believe that the extra tax revenues you will generate, compared to other businesses, will support the local community and environment in the longer term³.

#4. IRON & STEEL COMPANY: You are a local company. You would like to buy the land outright with the intention of developing an iron mine on site. Iron is your only specialty, and you are not interested in other types of minerals. You plan is to install an iron extraction site, and a steel fabrication and manufacturing facility adjacent to the iron site, in addition to a medium-sized research and training center. The environmental location will be attractive especially for the training center. The research and training facility is intended to be a national learning center with focus on iron extraction, iron metallurgy, steel manufacturing, local steel marketing & sales, iron & steel safety standards, clean environmental technology for iron & steel, and other themes focused on local iron and steel business. You plan to host regular meetings of the National Iron Association at your center. Memberships in your new research center, student internships from colleges and universities, and research fellowships, are within your future plans. You are aware of a global mining company interested to buy Ms. Meribrown's parcel, but you believe you have the support of the local community due to your good local reputation for safety and clean production (also see **footnote 3**).

³ A recent report by PwC (PriceWaterhouseCoopers) revealed that the top financial returns on investment for minerals is gold, magnesium, copper, iron, and coal (from best performer to least performer). Highlights of the report included three main recommendations: (1) an extended business involvement in the mineral supply chain is highly recommended, from start of extraction to finished goods, and (2) the industry needs to attract young talent, who are currently interested more in IT and digital manufacturing projects (such as in steel manufacturing), and (3) mergers and acquisitions are recommended to achieve economies of scale. The report added that more accurate cost estimation in feasibility studies is of critical importance. In retrospect, iron ore production may not be much profitable compared to other minerals, but the report mentions high profitability when iron ore investment extends its supply chain into metal production and steel manufacturing.

#5. HOTEL & GOOD TIMES RESORT: You own a small 15-room resort called Good Times Resort, located right on Wonder Lake itself. Your family manages and lives in this resort. It is highly seasonal and adequately successful resort so far. You are highly interested to buy Ms. Meribrown's parcel for two reasons: 1) You want to maintain the existing community style of Wonder Lake, such that your resort stays peaceful and family friendly, while you minimize the risk of mining company disruptions on the community and wildlife area. 2) Good Times Resort is in dire need of expansion. Your expansion plans are carefully crafted, and include expansion towards a more modern tourist site with water sports, such as snorkeling and diving. A franchise agreement with one of the largest hotel chains in the world is in plan. You have been targeting *Starwood Hotels & Resorts* which is part of Marriott Worldwide Hotel Chains, and some elementary talks have already begun – even before Mr. Meribrown's announcement to sell her parcel. Although the current location of Good Times Resort is directly opposite the parcel from the lake, yet you plan on constructing and developing a much bigger and more commercial 100 room hotel residence, in partnership with Marriott Worldwide Hotel Chains, and which will be located next the highway. You plan to still keep the current family-style resort with some renovations. Also, you are planning to build a wooden water bridge to link the two resort locations together, with lots of ideas on commercial activities on that bridge. You believe this expansion project has low risk, high returns, and maintains the community environment.

#6. RESTAURANT & SPORTS COMPLEX - You would like to buy the land to establish a medium-sized restaurant and a golf club business, capturing the highlights of the Wonder Lake area. Moreover, you plan to expand the golf club business in the future, to be a fully fledged Sports Complex with multiple sports activities and sports tournaments. You plan to establish the following sports courts in the following sequential order: (1) tennis – (2) football – (3) basketball – (4) volleyball – (5) swimming – and (6) a specialized gym. The sequential order is planned such that as time develops you accrue enough revenues to establish a new sports activity. However, you are flexible, and other sports activities are possible as well. You see Ms. Meribrown's parcel as a strategic location for your restaurant, and an ideal location for a very successful Sports Club business – knowing that the nearest sports club is 100 miles away. Thus, you plan to serve 100 miles of territory, much beyond the Wonder Lake community. You anticipate a successful restaurant business especially that it is along the Highway. Yet, you are aware of the large overhead and waste management costs associated with your planned business. Your initial idea is to have a specialized fish restaurant, given the Wonder Lake environment, but you are flexible to tap into more diverse tastes. A multi-restaurant outlet is another possibility as well.

#7. ZOO, MUSEUM, AND NATURAL WILDLIFE CONSERVATION CENTER:

You are interested in buying the land to establish three projects: open zoo, museum, and wildlife center. These three projects are inter-related with the following objectives: 1) to establish an animal museum, highlighting the learning aspects of Wonder Lake's botanical and animal species. Two pavilions are planned: botanical and wildlife. Within the wildlife pavilion, a special exhibition of the *Red Panda* will be organized. The *Red Panda Exhibition* is expected to attract most attention from kids and youngsters, as well as specialized animal scientists and animal rights activist groups. 2) To preserve the community in terms of its wilderness and natural habitats, while establishing an "Open Zoo". You plan to have an Open Zoo with a modest entrance fee, where some animals will be "on the open" while others are caged. The Open Zoo and museum will be linked together in multiple joint activities. 3) To establish a recognized Natural Wildlife Conservation Center, which will be hosting conferences around the year in its conference hall, establishing public debates, and a large-screen digital cinema with movie series called "Wildlife Digital Discoveries". Part of the movie series will be linked to the *Red Panda*, and the Panda animal species in general. Your three projects (zoo, museum, and wildlife center) are planned to be used by local schools, community colleges, senior citizens, wildlife association meetings, and other groups. Funding is expected to be based on an endowment fund, which will be partially based on government public financing. Additionally, you expect to pay very low interest rate on bank loans for your project, due to the government subsidizing interest loans to animal conservation projects. Also, once established, you expect to receive large R&D grants targeting animal conservation. Your bottom-line is not only financial, since you personally value animal conservation very much, and you value environmental service to the community.

#8. INTERNATIONAL SCHOOL– You are excited about building an internationally accredited school in this safe neighborhood. It is an excellent location for a private IB (International Baccalaureate) school. You do understand that there is a baby nursery 3 miles away, but it is small and highly focused on nursery service only. Your plan is to build a reputable school with an International Baccalaureate (IB) curriculum, up to the 12th grade, with special reputation on environmental science. Your timeline over the next years will be to implement your school plan in several timeline phases. The international accreditation of the IB is a fundamental necessity to your project. This requires hefty up-front costs. The time gap between revenues and costs is an expected challenge which you will need to address. Needed facilities to be considered for IB school accreditation include constructing a good library with adequate books collection, minimum number of classrooms, a playground, a sports center, computer and printing center, teacher rooms, food outlets, and a student lounge. Expensive high-tech science lab equipment related to environmental sciences is a strategic target you want to achieve. This includes biotech equipment, nano-tech equipment, and others. You have analyzed the schooling market, and there is high demand for IB degrees because they have a balance between pure academia (hard skills) and community projects (soft skills). You are a strong advocate of such balanced education. Furthermore, investing in human capital is beyond just financials, because it has long term impacts on the country's development, as well as on the personal life journey of each and every student you will serve.

Photo 1: Wonder Lake territory with “Black Granite” natural deposits

Photo 2: The flora species at Wonder Lake

Photo 3: The National *Highway 30*, which includes passenger cars as well as commercial trucks - almost all year round. It has a good rest area 1.5 miles away from the land parcel.

Photo 4: Animal species near Wonder Lake. Wildlife includes normal habitats, plus a semi-rare red panda species which originated from Chinese breeds (bottom left) classified as *Red Ailurus Fulgens Class II Panda Bear*, also known as “*The Red Panda*”. The Red Panda species is considered very special by lake visitors.

Photo 5: Good Times Resort is a moderately successful business, run by a family living within the resort. They would like to expand the resort towards a more modern tourism site, capturing Wonder Lake’s beautiful environmental scenery and amenities. Water sports are planned if the resort is expanded.

Photo 6: The Dairy Farm is very near to Ms. Meribrown’s land parcel. This is an already successful farm business, with potential to expand into other lines of farming, breeding, and possibly, a large farm shopping outlet.

Glacial Usage Map of Wonder Lake, Wadena District

Wonder Lake is located in Wadena District, a small Midwestern community. Wadena lobes are naturally extended land areas which have multiple land uses, ranging from agriculture to mining, to real estate, and other feasibility projects.

MAP #1: The beautiful Wonder Lake partitions the surrounding land area into two regions: green and white. The “green side” of the lake is characterized by original glacial sand and well sorted gravel, with tropical outwash areas. Mrs. Meribrown’s land parcel is amid the green side of the lake – although not all of the green area is actually green. On the other side of Wonder Lake is the “white side” which is characterized by medium sized rocks and till clay.

Geologic Map of Wonder Lake

MAP #2: Land area with natural geological resources of iron, magnesium and copper. The natural iron is roughly one-third of Mrs. Meribrown’s land parcel. Two-thirds of the land parcel is covered with natural gabbroic incursions of magnesium and copper. It is known that magnesium and copper have high financial returns, yet require massive initial investment. On the other hand, a combined project of iron extraction with steel manufacturing is considered a lower risk, high return investment.

MAP #3: Neighborhood map of Wonderlake showing Mrs. Meribrown’s land parcel, the nearby dairy farm, highway transportation, Good Times resort, the lake, Town Hall, water supply, and private home residences. A nearby town has a population of three thousand inhabitants.

Script of Mrs. Meribrown's Phone Conversation with Lawyer

LAWYER

Hello, Mrs. Meribrown. How are you doing?

MRS. MERIBROWN

Hello. I am doing fine.

LAWYER

I am calling regarding the land parcel you wanna sell ... I believe it is close to the lake? Correct?

MRS. MERIBROWN

I own this parcel overseeing Wonder Lake, given to me from my grandfather. I actually inherited this parcel from him. Now it is your duty to make sure that the land will be utilized wisely. The land is 500 acres in a beautiful neighborhood overlooking Wonder Lake.

LAWYER

Sure I will do my best, ma'am. So.. you wanna sell it for a particular purpose? As far as my recollection goes, I recall your late husband wanted to do business in it and he --

MRS. MERIBROWN (interrupting)

Ohh! You remind me of Roger! Roger had lots of ideas. He was very excited about uplifting this neighborhood to a wider scale than it currently is. His excitement lives with me until today! You know, he was not in the very best of health during his last days. Quite frankly, he also knew that .. seriously speaking, it is not that simple! The land can have many, many different uses and so many different people would want to join in with him.

LAWYER (commenting)

I confirm. He wanted to make sure about the project on the land. Not just sell the land.

MRS. MERIBROWN

What do you mean? (serious voice tone)

LAWYER

I apologize for interrupting...

MRS. MERIBROWN

No, it is okay, but what do you mean?

LAWYER

I meant that Roger, God bless his soul, would have been very selective on the selling process. He wouldn't sell the land easily at all!

MRS. MERIBROWN

That is true. (pausing for a breathe of remembrance). And I am here to make sure that the land will be sold for a purpose. A good purpose. A purpose which will uplift the neighborhood to a different level. Not just commercially. I mean... the community... the impact... on the people... on the country.

LAWYER

So ma-aam, how do you want me to proceed?

MRS. MERIBROWN

Make an ad. The ad would be about selling the land for a good purpose. Not just money. Although, well, .. more money is still good... no doubt about that... but I will not sell-off my land and community without a genuine purpose! So, you should post an ad calling for a good project to be carried out over my land. The project must be financially secure and sustainable, and at the same time, with an equal weight I presume, it must deliver good community impact. I tell you. Safe. Green. Lively. And profitable. Yah, that's it! Basically, I want to sell for a purpose... and I require a good purpose.

LAWYER

Great. I thank you a lot, I mean, for your confidence and trust in me. I will accordingly implement. First, I will do the ad... and then, I will collect the best fit responses and let you know. I already see good things coming out of this land... Let me assure you, ma-am, .. I am sure we will end up with a fantastic project which is both profitable and has admirable community impacts.

MRS. MERIBROWN

That will be just fantastic. Agreed. Will wait your call in a few weeks. Goodbye.

LAWYER

Goodbye, ma'am.

Ads for Mrs. Meribrown's Land Parcel

Ad #1: Daily Newspaper (Print)

Daily newspaper, 2nd page, thick Box, 3 days

START Ad

Good Purpose Project
500 acre LAND PARCEL
Requires a Feasibility Proposal
for a Profitable Project with
Good Community Impact
Email: meribrown@estate.gmail.com

END Ad

Ad #2: Business Magazine (Print)

Business magazine, 1/2 page, all-bold text, normal tier ad,
title underline, two dotted lines extra, no Box, 2 weekly issues

START Ad

(one line space for emphasis)

... (dotted line)

REQUEST FOR PROJECT PROPOSALS

500 Acre LAND PARCEL

Land Parcel overlooking beautiful Wonder Lake scenery.

On Strategic location with tropical and sand/gravel earth.

Land also contains natural deposits of iron, magnesium and copper.

This is a tender call for profitable proposals with good community impacts.

One of the following lines of business are invited for feasibility proposals: (1) real-estate, (2) dairy farm, (3) mining, (4) metal manufacturing, (5) hotel resort, (6) restaurant with golf & sports club complex, (7) zoo/museum with wildlife conservatory, (8) international school.

Project Proposals must prove financial sustainability and responsible community impacts. Best fit proposals will be contacted.

Email: meribrown@estate.gmail.com

... (dotted line)

END Ad

Ad #3: Online Web Host (Digital)

- Duration:** Two weeks, 24/7 online access
- Purpose:** Request for Project Proposals
- Location:** Land Parcel (500 acres) with direct access to Wonder Lake and neighborhood areas, close to Highway 30.
- Business:** Real Estate; Farming and Groceries; Mining (Natural Deposits); Iron & Metal; Hotels and Resorts; Restaurants / Sports Facilities; Zoo and Wildlife Conservation; Education (Schooling).
- Description:** This is a request for feasibility proposals. The project proposals must reflect a strong value-added convincing argument towards project feasibility and sustainability from financial and economic/community perspectives. Criteria to be used to select the best-fit proposals include financial sustainability and good community impacts. Your proposal must address one line of business from the drop-down list below.
//Drop-down-menu-extracted-from-fields=Business//.
- Email:** meribrown@estate.gmail.com
- Upload Files:** 3 files
MAP1(file), MAP2(file), MAP3(file)
//3 files successfully uploaded //.

- Comments:** Submit your feasibility proposal as ONE file in PDF format.
- Submitter:** Attention of Mr. Eric Marinos, Lawyer, JD.

WRITTEN FEASIBILITY REPORT General Outline

- ❖ COVER PAGE: university logo, course/professor, Project Title, team members, date.
- ❖ EXECUTIVE SUMMARY (500 words).
- 1. INTRODUCTION:
 - a. Background information
 - b. Project Vision Statement
 - c. Timeline phases of your project
- 2. PROJECT COMPONENTS: Description of main project components and tasks.
- 3. DESIGN LAYOUT: Physical Design Layout of the project is required based on AEIOUX.
- 4. MARKET ANALYSIS:
 - a. Five Forces: 1- Competition and Rivalry, 2- Buyers Demand and Customer Value, 3- Input Suppliers and Supply Chain, 4- Entry/Exit Conditions, and 5- Substitutes and Complements. Use 4 or 5 bullets for each of the five forces. Besides each bullet, use plus (+), minus (-), or neutral (N) impact of the bullet on your project's profitability.
 - b. Summary Table is required
- 5. FINANCIAL PROFITABILITY & PRICING:
 - a. Explain the main financial cash flows (costs, benefits, reinvestments, asset acquisition, salvage liquidation, etc.).
 - b. Diagram of financial timeline (no numbers needed) using up-arrows as cash inflows, and down-arrows as cash outflows. A 20-year project lifetime is recommended. Describe your reasoning underneath the financial cash flows. Locate your expected time to "break-even" on the financial timeline.
 - c. State and describe the pricing method you will use across the 20 years.
 - d. Write a summary paragraph for financial assessment and sustainable profitability.
- 6. COMMUNITY/ECONOMIC IMPACT:
 - a. Outline the project's *positive* impacts and *negative* impacts on the community. Community/economic impact factors to include are: negative externalities (e.g. pollution), positive externalities (e.g. human capital, R&D), community development, natural habitat conservation, safety, quality of life, waste management, impact on employment, impact on country trade balance (imports and exports), impact on GDP (C+I+G+X-M over the project's timeline), and other factors as deemed appropriate.
 - b. A GDP summary table is required.
 - c. Write a paragraph for the overall project impact on the community/economy.
- 7. PROJECT RISK:
 - a. Identify the major project risks, and describe the mitigation actions to be taken to minimize those risks.
 - b. RAM matrix.
 - c. A risk/mitigation summary table is required at the end of this section.
- 8. CONCLUSION: Provide an overall assessment of your project with solid convincing arguments towards its feasibility. What is the core value added of your project relative to others? How does the financial profitability and community/economic impacts reinforce each other in your project? Why is your project the best alternative?
- ❖ REFERENCES: Harvard/APA Style.
- ❖ APPENDIX (Optional).

Important Guidelines:

- Length should be approximately 5,000 words (minimum 4,000 words, and maximum 7,000 words).
- Use headings and sub-headings based on above outline.
- Write the Executive Summary after finishing your report.
- Spell-check your report.
- Check grammar and logical reasoning.
- Insert page numbers.
- Proof-read before submission.